

123 YEARS OF PASTEUR INSTITUTE NIŠ

55th DAYS OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE

INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

26-29. 09. 2023.
NIŠ, SERBIA

ORGANISED BY

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FACULTY OF MEDICINE NIŠ

PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE NIŠ

SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY OF NIŠ

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POSTER PRESENTATION

INFLUENZA VIRUS SUBTYPES CIRCULATING IN VOJVODINA, SERBIA DURING THE 2022/2023 SEASON

Maja Tomic¹, Gordana Kovacevic¹, Nina Djordjevic Bjelanovic¹, Natasa Skoric¹, Natasa Nikolic^{1,2}, Ivana Hrnjakovic Cvjetkovic^{1,2}, Branka Basica¹, Lidija Terzic¹, Andrea Bogdanov¹, Aleksandra Patric^{1,2}

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Objectives: Influenza virus can cause severe respiratory illness related to morbidity and mortality worldwide. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of influenza A and B viruses in ambulatory and hospital patients with flu symptoms during the 2022/2023 season.

Methods: A total of 1394 combined nasal and throat swab samples from patients with acute respiratory symptoms in Vojvodina during the 2022/2023 season were analyzed. Extraction of RNA was performed using QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit. Influenza virus was detected using rRT-PCR CDC Influenza SARS-CoV-2 Multiplex Assay and then subtyped with CDC primers.

Results: The overall prevalence was 19.7%, with 53.7% of the samples positive for influenza A and 46.3% for influenza B. The dominant subtype was A (H1N1)pdm09 (80.1%), followed by A(H3N2) (19.9%). All influenza B-positive samples belonged to Victoria lineages. The highest prevalence of influenza A and B was in the 30–64 age-group. Influenza A had a higher prevalence than influenza B in both ambulatory and hospital samples, 52.2% and 55.6%, respectively. February was the peak month for influenza activity, with 37.9% of the total positive samples.

Conclusion: Considering the results, continuous surveillance of influenza virus subtypes is necessary to predict seasonal trends and prepare for potential influenza outbreaks.

Keywords: Influenza, RT-PCR, Prevalence, Vojvodina